

1 **An expression screen to identify genes important for trastuzumab resistance: *lrx4*.**

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6 We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in patients sensitive or resistant to treatment with
7 trastuzumab for HER2+ breast cancer for discovery of genes that confer or support resistance to
8 HER2-targeted therapies in humans. In this manuscript we describe identification of *lrx4* as a candidate
9 gene product of the trastuzumab resistance gene expression signature.

10 Citations

11 1. Bao, Z.Z., Bruneau, B.G., Seidman, J.G., Seidman, C.E. and Cepko, C.L., 1999. Regulation of
12 chamber-specific gene expression in the developing heart by *lrx4*. *Science*, 283(5405), pp.1161-1164.